

NEUROPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF COW COLOSTRUM In PENTYLENETETRAZOLE-INDUCED MODEL Of SEIZURE In MICE

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Epilepsy is a chronic neurological condition in which groups of neurons, in the brain periodically transmit incorrect signals, leading to seizures. Oxidative stress and cognitive impairment are associated with Pentylenetetrazole (PTZ) -induced seizure. Cow colostrum (CC), a nutraceutical found in the first milk produced by female animals after childbirth, is known for its antioxidant properties. In this study, we assessed its effects on PTZ-induced seizures.

Material and methods: The experimental protocol comprised of six groups (n = 8), where mice were pretreated with cow colostrum (125, 250, 500 mg/kg orally) 45 minutes before, or sodium valproate (250 mg/kg intraperitoneally) 30 minutes prior to PTZ administration (80 mg/kg, intraperitoneally) and seizure episode was note for 30 min. Behavioral changes were compared at 2 time points, before and after PTZ administration. The mean value of all the tests were compared and the results were analyzed using One-way ANOVA test, followed by multiple comparison using Sidak's and Dunnett's test.

Results: PTZ triggered myoclonic jerks and generalized tonic-clonic seizures (GTCS). Our findings revealed that cow colostrum significantly delayed the onset of both myoclonic jerks and GTCS. It also shortened seizure duration, reduced the interictal period, and lowered seizure scores. Additionally, at the highest dose, it protected 25% of the mice from seizures. Furthermore, it reduced brain Malondialdehyde (MDA) levels and preserved Glutathione (GSH) levels. Pretreatment also improved cognition and memory retention in mice, as observed in the elevated plus maze and open field tests.

Conclusion: Our results underscore the antioxidant and anticonvulsant properties of cow colostrum. It appears that cow colostrum inhibits reactive oxygen/nitrogen species ROS/RNS activity, thereby producing anticonvulsant effects and mitigating cognitive impairment.

Keywords:

Epilepsy, pentylenetetrazole, Cow colostrum, oxidative stress, cognitive impairment, GABA

Abbreviations:

PTZ: Pentylenetetrazole

MDA: Malondialdehyde

GSH: Glutathione

SV: Sodium valproate

GTCS: Generalized tonic-clonic seizure

C.C: Cow colostrum

ROS: Reactive oxygen species

AED: Anti-epileptic drug

TBARS: Thiobarbituric acid reactive substance

1. INTRODUCTION:

Epilepsy is a common neurological disorder and estimated with a prevalence of 0.5–1.5% in the general population varying between developed countries and developing countries [1]. It is characterized by recurrent seizures, loss of consciousness [2], cognitive impairment[3], autonomic motor episodes[4], or a combination of these symptoms[5]. According to International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) an epileptic seizure is caused by abnormal, excessive, and synchronous neuronal activity in the different brain areas and presenting various signs and/or symptoms accordingly [6]. Epilepsy is typified by repeated seizures and the aberrant firing of neurons located mainly in the cerebral cortex and often under unprovoked conditions. The burst firing neurons accompanied with epileptic discharges could result in a variety of changes at the cellular level, e.g., activation of glutamate receptors, alteration of γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptor, activation of cytokine expression, increased oxidative stress, modification of neurogenesis, adjustment of plasticity or stimulation of some late cell death pathways [7]. There is evidence that the formation of reactive species or the decreased activity of antioxidant systems may result in different forms of epilepsy as well as increased chances of repeating epileptic seizures [8].

Regardless, the abundance of antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) introduced after phenobarbitone (PB) in the beginning of the previous century, nowadays 20–30% of patients with epilepsy still continue having seizures [9]. Furthermore, during metabolic processes, numerous AEDs, especially from the older AEDs generation, including PB, phenytoin (PHT) and carbamazepine (CBZ), produce reactive metabolites which can covalently bind to different endogenous macromolecules or increase the formation of reactive oxygen

species (ROS) that can induce oxidative damage and cause toxicity. There are numerous studies evaluating the influence of epilepsy and AEDs on the formation of free radicals, show that either of them could be connected to oxidative stress generation[9].

Reactive oxygen species are produced during normal cellular metabolism. Sources include leakage of electrons from the mitochondrial electron transport chain onto molecular oxygen resulting in formation of superoxide ($O_2 \cdot^-$), cytochrome P450, xanthine oxidase, autoxidation reactions involving catecholamines with O_2 to form $O_2 \cdot^-$, activated phagocytes that produce $O_2 \cdot^-$, hypochlorous acid, and hydrogen peroxide [10]. Increased generation of reactive oxygen species occurs because of mitochondrial dysfunction as in neuro degenerative diseases [11] and epilepsy [12], and during inflammation and tissue damage [13]. The major antioxidants in the cell are the enzymes superoxide dismutase, catalases and glutathione peroxidase. In addition, antioxidants include the low molecular weight scavengers of free radicals [14].

Cow colostrum is an antioxidant having multifactorial effect. It is the first milk produced by female animals after giving birth[15]. Nourishing neonate with antibodies, growth factors, and nutrition like as proteins, carbs, lipids, vitamins, and minerals. Vitamins (A, C, E), lactoperoxidase, lactoferrin and glutathione in colostrum helps in reducing the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [16]. Glutathione is referred to as the ultimate antioxidant source [17]. Lactoperoxidase, the other component found in cow colostrum catalyses the oxidation of H_2O_2 generating reactive products with significant antibacterial activity[18]. Lactoferrin, in turn, functions as a non-enzymatic antioxidant by attaching to iron (Fe) created during the breakdown process or cellular inflammation[19], lowering hydroxyl radical generation[20]. Recent studies have also focused on the overall effects of cow colostrum under oxidative stress, including its neuroprotective impact [21]. Cow colostrum has multifactorial effects including anti-inflammatory and antioxidant[22]. Neuronal cell death due to N-methyl-d-aspartic acid [23] in the rodent hippocampus was dramatically reduced by cow colostrum therapy[24].

PTZ is a gamma aminobutyric acid (GABA)-A receptor antagonist [25]. First used by Everett and Richard in 1946. PTZ seizure subsequently mimic to absence seizures and generalized tonic-clonic seizure in humans [26]. PTZ binds to to the benzodiazepine site and inhibits the influx of Cl^- ions inside the postsynaptic neuron [27] and downregulation of GABAergic tone[28], leading to increased neuronal activity. This regulation causes generalized seizures in animals [29]. PTZ-induced seizures cause significant neuronal injury[30], oxidative stress[31], increased DNA damage, nitric oxide production [32], and expression of the pro-inflammatory Tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) [33]. A single injection of a convulsive dose of PTZ also induces acute seizure. The aim of the present study therefore, was to investigate the effect of cow colostrum on seizure development, oxidative stress and cognitive impairment in PTZ-induced seizure.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Animals

Swiss albino male mice (22–26 g) were procured from Animal House Facility, Amity Institute of Pharmacy, Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Noida. Animals were housed under controlled conditioning ($22\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, 55–65% relative humidity and 12 h dark/light cycles). After 7 days of acclimatization to laboratory conditions, the animals were randomly assigned to experimental groups, 8 mice each. Food and water were allowed *ad libitum* during the study period. All tests were performed between 9:00 a.m. and 3:00 p.m. to minimize circadian influences on seizure susceptibility[34]. All the experimental procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC approval no. CPCSEA/IAEC/AIP/2022/12/19) and were conducted according to the guidelines of the Committee for Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA), New Delhi, India.

2.2. Experimentation

Fig.1. A graphical view of the experimental design. Abbreviations: SAL: saline, PTZ: Pentylenetetrazole, C.C: Cow colostrum, MDA: malondialdehyde, GSH: Glutathione.

In this study, the effect of PTZ on induction of seizure in animals was investigated. Mice was injected with 80 mg/kg; i.p. PTZ dissolved in 0.9% (w/v) normal saline (Fig. 1). The animals were observed for 30 min post-PTZ injection using Racine Scale. All the animals were divided into 6 groups. Group 1 was vehicle-treated normal control group, in which no PTZ injection was given and only the vehicle was injected. Group 2 was vehicle treated PTZ control group, in which PTZ was injected. Group 3 to 5 were the treatment groups in which cow colostrum was administered in three doses as 125 mg/kg; p.o., 250 mg/kg; p.o. and 500 mg/kg;

p.o., 7 days prior to PTZ injection respectively. The last Group VI was positive control group in which sodium valproate (250 mg/kg; i.p.) was administered 30 min prior to PTZ injection[35].

2.3. Drugs, chemicals and materials:

All the drug solutions and suspensions were freshly prepared before use. Pentylenetetrazole- PTZ (Sigma Chemical Co.), cow colostrum, sodium valproate (Elfin Drugs, India). Drugs were administered intraperitoneally (*IP*), except for cow colostrum that was given orally (*PO*). All solutions were administered in a volume of 0.1ml/10g of body weight.

2.4. Seizure Scoring:

PTZ was injected at a dose of 80 mg/kg; i.p., to induce seizures in mice [36]. This specific dose was responsible for inducing seizures in every animal subjected to the treatment. The animals were situated within a Plexiglas enclosure measuring 20 × 20 × 20 cm. A 30-minute observation period followed, during which parameters such as latency to GTCS, the frequency of GTCS, mortality, duration of inter-ictal period and GTCS were monitored. Any animals that survived were considered to have protective effects.

The animals were observed for 30 minutes after PTZ challenge. Seizure activity was evaluated using Racine scale as mentioned below[37]:

Stage 0: no response

Stage 1: hyperactivity, vibrissae twitching.

Stage 2: head nodding, head clonus and myoclonic jerk

Stage 3: unilateral forelimb clonus

Stage 4: rearing with bilateral forelimb clonus.

Stage 5: generalized tonic-clonic seizure (GTCS) with loss of righting reflex.

The observations were done based on the GTCS shown by the animal. The number of myoclonic jerks, latencies to myoclonic jerks and GTCS were recorded[38]. The median of the seizure stages was calculated to all groups after each PTZ injection[39]. The animals were observed for straub tail, myoclonic jerks, and occurrence of generalized tonic-clonic seizure (GTCS) with loss righting reflex, for 30 minutes after PTZ-injection.

2.5. BEHAVIOURAL PARAMETERS:

2.5.1. Open field:

The open field test was utilized to assess locomotion activity and fecal boli/defecation as indications of stress or anxiety[40]. The test setup comprised of a square arena with a black floor, divided into 25

squares, enclosed by black Plexiglass walls. Among these squares, 16 adjacent to the walls constitute a sheltered region known as the 'arena periphery',[41] while the remaining 9 squares form an exposed area called the 'arena center'.

To acclimatize the mice, they were brought to the testing room along with their home cages, and a 30-minute acclimatization period was provided. Subsequently, a single mouse was taken from its home cage and placed into the open field arena[40]. The mouse was allowed to move freely within the respective quadrant of the maze for a 10-minute period, during which the tracking program recorded its movement [42]. Throughout the session, various conventional and ethological parameters were collected, including central area frequency and rearing[41].

2.5.2. EPM:

The EPM (Elevated Plus Maze) is a commonly used behavioral test to assess anxiety-like behavior in rodents. The maze consists of two open and two closed arms, each identical, extending from a central platform. Prior to the trial, mice were allowed to acclimatize to the testing facility for at least 7 days. During the test, a mouse was placed on the central platform, facing one of the open arms, and given the freedom to explore for five minutes. Mouse behaviors were continuously recorded using a video camera mounted above the maze. The recorded sessions were later scored using a program to generate data files suitable for statistical analysis[41]. Between trials, the maze was thoroughly cleaned with alcohol and water. In the first trial, the time it took for the mouse to enter a closed arm with all four limbs, when placed at the end of one open arm facing away from the central platform, was noted as the initial transfer latency. A maximum cutoff time of 60 seconds was set for this measure. After entering a closed arm or when the cutoff time was reached, the mouse was allowed to freely explore the maze, including both open and closed arms, for an additional 10 seconds. Twenty-four hours later or one hour later, a retention transfer latency test was performed following the same procedure as the initial test. The mouse was once again placed in the elevated plus maze. If the mouse did not enter a closed arm within 60 seconds during this second test, a transfer latency of 60 seconds was recorded for that trial[43].

2.6. OXIDATIVE STRESS ASSESSMENT:

The tissue was processed following the methods described in previous studies[44]. After completing the behavioral tests, the animals were euthanized. The entire brain was extracted, rinsed in isotonic saline, and weighed to determine oxidative parameters[45]. Tissue homogenates (10% w/v) were prepared in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The homogenate was then centrifuged at 15000 rpm for 20 minutes, and the resulting supernatant was used to measure lipid peroxidation and reduced glutathione levels[46]. Additionally, the homogenates were centrifuged at 10,000 ×g at 4 °C for 15 minutes, and aliquots of the supernatants were separated and utilized for biochemical analyses[47].

2.6.1. Lipid Peroxidation (MDA):

Malondialdehyde (MDA) acts as a biomarker for lipid peroxidation[48]. Brain tissue samples were used to determine the levels of Malondialdehyde (MDA) through the thiobarbituric acid reactive substance (TBARS) method, which is indicative of lipid peroxidation as per previously described methods [49]. In the experiment, 0.2 ml of homogenate supernatant was taken in a test tube[50]. To this, 1.5 ml of 20% (v/v) acetic acid at pH 3.5, 1.5 ml of 0.8% (w/v) thiobarbituric acid, and 0.2 ml of 8.1% (w/v) sodium dodecyl sulphate were added. The mixture was then heated at 95°C for 60 minutes[51]. After cooling, 5 ml of n-butanol-pyridine mixture (15:1 v/v) was added, and the tubes were centrifuged at 4000 g for 10 minutes. The spectrophotometric measurement of the developing pink color was taken at 532 nm. To determine the TBARS concentration, a standard calibration curve was constructed using 1-10 mm of 1, 1, 3, 3-tetramethoxy propane. The final TBARS values were reported in nanomoles per mg of protein[50].

2.6.2. Glutathione (GSH)

Glutathione was assessed utilizing the Ellman method[51]. The homogenate supernatant was combined with trichloroacetic acid (10% w/v) in a 1:1 ratio. The resulting mixture was then subjected to centrifugation at 1000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4 °C. Subsequently, 0.5 ml of the resulting supernatant was mixed with 2 ml of 0.3 M disodium hydrogen phosphate, followed by the addition of 0.25 ml of freshly prepared DTNB [5, 5'-dithiobis(2-nitrobenzoic acid) dissolved in 1% w/v sodium citrate][50]. After 15 minutes, the absorbance at 412 nm was measured using a spectrophotometer[51]. A standard curve was constructed using 10-100 µM of reduced glutathione, and the results were expressed as micromoles of reduced glutathione per mg of protein[50].

2.7. Statistical Analysis:

Graph Pad Prism (version 8.4.2) was used for all statistical analysis. values are expressed as mean ± sem. Statistical differences between the treatment and control groups were evaluated using unpaired t-test and one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparison using Sidak's and Dunnett's test. The value of $p < 0.05$ was considered to be significant.

3. Results:

3.1. PTZ-induced seizure:

In the PTZ group, all the animals displayed full Generalized Tonic-Clonic Seizures (GTCS). Prior administration of C.C did not offer any protection against GTCS at the doses of 125 and 250 mg/kg; p.o. However, cow colostrum at a dose of 500 mg/kg; p.o. provide 25% protection against PTZ-induced GTCS (Table. 1.). On the other hand, sodium valproate (250 mg/kg; i.p.) provided complete protection against seizures.

3.2. Cow colostrum significantly suppressed PTZ induced seizure in mice model.

Table 1: Effect of cow colostrum on suppressing PTZ induced seizure in mice model. Data represented as mean±sem, using unpaired t-test and one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparison using Sidak's and Dunnett's test. Comparison of latency of myoclonic jerks, latency of GTCS, frequency of GTCS, duration of seizure and interictal period between PTZ group with cow colostrum group. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; * represent comparison between PTZ group vs cow colostrum groups.

Groups	Latency to GTCS (s)	Frequency of GTCS	Duration of GTCS (s)	Interictal period (s)	Latency to Myoclonic jerks (s)	% Mortality	% Protection
PTZ	75.63 ± 1.83	3.38 ± 0.18	57.25 ± 4.06	328.75 ± 5.94	50.25 ± 0.72	25%	0
C.C 125 mg/kg; p.o.	144.63 ± 2.80***	2.63 ± 0.18*	35.75 ± 2.66*	397.13 ± 8.54***	126 ± 4.06**	12.5%	0
C.C 250 mg/kg; p.o.	211.75 ± 4.10***	2.25 ± 0.16**	26.13 ± 1.99***	578.13 ± 12.47***	196.5 ± 6.07***	0	0
C.C 500 mg/kg; p.o.	276.34 ± 2.71***	1.33 ± 0.21***	12.33 ± 2.20***	707.5 ± 12.5***	248.5 ± 4.04***	0	25%

All the animals showed complete GTCS in PTZ group. Pretreatment with cow colostrum showed 25% protection against PTZ-induced mortality at dose of 500 mg/kg; p.o, (Table 1). Complete protection against seizures was observed with valproate (250 mg/kg;i.p.). The latency to myoclonic jerks [$F(5,42) = 187.2, P < 0.001$] and GTCS [$F(5,42) = 1778, P < 0.001$] was increased significantly when cow colostrum was administered at all the doses (125, 250 and 500 mg/kg;p.o.), as compared to the PTZ group (Table 1). After Bartlett's statistic test, it was found that cow colostrum significantly decreased the frequency [$F(5,42) = 87.83, P < 0.001$]and duration of GTCS [$F(5,42) = 93.59, P < 0.001$], thus showing protection against oxidative stress induced seizure. Interictal period was found to significantly increased in cow colostrum groups as compared [$F(5,42) = 1218, P < 0.001$] as compared to PTZ group, showing protection against oxidative stress-induced seizure.

3.3. Effect of cow colostrum against PTZ induced cognition impairment in elevated plus maze:

Fig.2. : Effect of cow colostrum against PTZ induced cognition impairment in elevated plus maze. Data represented as mean±sem, using unpaired *t*-test and one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparison using Sidak's and Dunnett's test. Comparison of retention latency between control group with PTZ group and PTZ group with cow colostrum and sodium valproate group. @@@ $p < 0.001$; @ represents comparison between control group vs PTZ group. * $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$; * represent comparison between PTZ group vs cow colostrum groups and sodium valproate group.

No significant difference was observed in the initial transfer latency amongst the groups in PTZ model, whereas a significant difference was observed in the retention transfer latency between the groups [$F(5,42) = 187.2, P < 0.001$]. Retention transfer latency was found to be significantly increased in the PTZ group ($P < 0.001$) as compared to vehicle control group, thus showing an impairment of memory in the PTZ group. A significant decrease in the retention transfer latency was observed in cow colostrum (125, 250 and 500 mg/kg) treated groups (Fig. 2) as compared to the PTZ group, showing an improvement in memory retention. Similarly, the standard drug valproate also caused significant decrease in the retention transfer latency as compared to the PTZ group and the values were comparable to that of the cow colostrum pre-treated groups

3.4. Effect of cow colostrum against PTZ induced anxiolytic potential in the open field test:

Fig.3. : Effect of cow colostrum against PTZ induced anxiolytic potential in the open field test. Data represented as mean±sem, using unpaired t-test and one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparison using Sidak's and Dunnett's test. Comparison of frequency of central entry and rearing between control group with PTZ group and PTZ group with cow colostrum and sodium valproate group. @@@ $p < 0.001$; @ represents comparison between control group vs PTZ group. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; * represent comparison between PTZ group vs cow colostrum groups and sodium valproate group.

In PTZ model, significant decrease in the central entry [$F(5,42)=107.5$, $P < 0.001$] and rearing [$F(5,42)=121.6$, $P < 0.001$] was observed between groups. In comparison to vehicle control group. After Bartlett's statistic test, it was found that central entry and rearing was decreased significantly in PTZ group ($P < 0.001$) in comparison to the vehicle control group. Cow colostrum pre-treatment and valproate significantly increased the central entry as compared to the PTZ group (Fig. 3).

3.5. Effect of cow colostrum on the levels of GSH in PTZ-induced seizure in mice:

Fig.4. : Effect of cow colostrum on the levels of GSH in PTZ-induced seizure in mice. Data represented as mean±sem, using unpaired *t*-test and one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparison using Sidak's and Dunnett's test. Comparison of levels of GSH between control group with PTZ group and PTZ group with cow colostrum and sodium valproate group. @@@ $p < 0.001$; @ represents comparison between control group vs PTZ group. *** $p < 0.001$; * represent comparison between PTZ group vs cow colostrum groups and sodium valproate group.

In PTZ-induced seizure, a significant difference was observed in the reduced glutathione levels between the groups [F(5,24)=74.06, $P < 0.001$]. A significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) in the GSH levels was observed in PTZ group as compared to vehicle control group. Cow colostrum pre-treatment reversed the PTZ-induced decrease in GSH levels at all dose levels tested (Fig. 4). The increase in GSH in cow colostrum pre-treated groups was found to be comparable to that of the valproate group

3.6. Effect of cow colostrum on the levels of MDA in PTZ-induced seizure in mice:

Fig.5. : Effect of cow colostrum on the levels of MDA in PTZ-induced seizure in mice. Data represented as mean \pm sem, using unpaired *t*-test and one-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparison using Sidak's and Dunnett's test. Comparison of levels of MDA between control group with PTZ group and PTZ group with cow colostrum and sodium valproate group. @@@ p <0.001; @ represents comparison between control group vs PTZ group. ** p <0.01; *** p <0.001; * represent comparison between PTZ group vs cow colostrum groups and sodium valproate group.

A significant difference was found in the brain MDA levels in between the groups [F(5,24)=182.4, P <0.001]. Bartlett's statistic test revealed that MDA level was significantly increased in PTZ group (P <0.001) as compared to the vehicle control group. Reversal of the increased MDA levels was observed in cow colostrum pre-treated groups in comparison to the PTZ group (Fig. 5).

4. Discussion:

Epilepsy is one of the most common neurological disorders that is still in need of safer drugs and improved drug with less adverse effect/reactions. It is characterized by recurring seizures [52], loss of consciousness [2], cognitive impairment [3], autonomic motor episodes [4], or a combination of these symptoms [53]. Existing anti-epileptic drugs (AED's) have been associated with cognitive impairments and increased oxidative stress [54] in epileptic patients with prolong use. This highlights the need for an AED

with multifactorial effect while minimizing or eliminating side effects. Cow colostrum (CC), also known as bovine colostrum, is the first mammary lacteal secretion[55], used for both medicinal and dietary purposes[16]. Colostrum contains minerals, hormones, growth factors, and enzymes with antioxidant[56], anti-inflammatory [57]and antibacterial action[58]. It has the ability to cross the blood-brain barrier and is therefore useful for treating neurological diseases like Alzheimer's disease [59] as well as neuronal injuries such cerebral ischemia reperfusion injury[60] and intracerebral haemorrhage, etc[35].

In the present study, cow colostrum was used in three doses of 125, 250 and 500 mg/kg; p.o. to assess its effect in reducing seizures and related oxidative stress. The seizure was induced by giving PTZ (80 mg/kg) intraperitoneally to mice in PTZ vehicle control group as well as in treatment groups and standard group. The seizure episodes culminated into generalized tonic-clonic seizure, mimicking generalized seizure and absence seizure in humans [61]. Animal behavior is preferably observed for 30 minutes or at least 6-10 h after PTZ injection, especially once the seizure score reaches 3 or higher. In addition, the relating changes in seizure duration and latency to time and seizure severity [62].

Cow colostrum at the highest dose, protected 25% of the mice from seizures (Table 1.). It doses dependently showed anti-convulsant activity via blocking the action of ROS/RNS activity on GABA production. Additionally it increased the interictal period, reduced the duration and frequency of GTCS. It also delayed the latency of both myoclonic jerks and GTCS (Table. 1), signifying seizure suppression effects possible inhibiting the ROS/RNS production and oxidative stress. Cow colostrum has demonstrated its ability to decrease hippocampal apoptotic cell death[63], edema and neurotoxicity[64] caused by N-methyl-d-aspartic acid in a dose-dependent manner[65]. Therefore, the mortality rate was comparatively lower than the PTZ-group (Table 1.).

One of the triggers for epileptogenesis involves the influx of Ca^{2+} through NMDA receptors, subsequently activating NADPH oxidase enzymes [66]. This activation leads to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [67] and peroxynitrite[68], which oxidize glutathione[69], and consequently damage neurons. Additionally, increased levels of ROS and superoxide production within the brain can directly inhibit the enzyme glutamine synthase, leading to generalized tonic-clonic seizures [70]. Furthermore, the generation of free radicals can enhance seizure activity by causing an abnormal accumulation of the excitatory neurotransmitter glutamic acid [71]. In this study, progressive brain damage is associated with increased levels of markers for oxidative stress[72], seizures trigger the production of free radicals, resulting in lipid peroxidation [73], [74]. Previous studies have also shown that PTZ-induced seizures lead to elevated levels of malondialdehyde (MDA) [75], which serves as an oxidative stress marker[76], along with a significant reduction in levels of glutathione (GSH) [77], in animals signified substantial brain oxidative stress [78] responsible for behavioural alteration[79]. GSH is a crucial antioxidant enzyme which playing a critical role in protecting cells from oxidative stress and maintaining overall cellular health [80]. Pre-treatment with sodium valproate maintained GSH levels in the brain and substantially reduced the lipid peroxidation caused due to increased MDA levels[81]. Cow colostrum being an antioxidant has the potential to reduce MDA levels (Fig. 5) and elevate GSH levels (Fig. 4). It also exhibited a dose dependent

neurotherapeutic potential by preventing neurotoxicity and reducing brain oxidative stress caused due to PTZ [16].

Many studies have reported PTZ-induced seizures have results in anxiety, impaired cognitive function, and memory retention difficulties [82]. Behavioral impairment is catalyzed through molecular and cellular imbalances. In present study also, PTZ-induced seizure shown induced anxiety, memory and cognitive impairments was observed consistently to the previous findings. High retention transfer latency in elevated plus maze test [83], [84] and low recognition index in object recognition test in the PTZ kindled animals earmarked cognition impairment and anxiety in the diseased animals [28]. Significant alteration in behavior and induced anxiety has also been linked with reduced exploration and locomotion in the open field test [85] which was also observed in the PTZ group in this study. Progressive behavioral decline was also evident through deteriorated spatial memory retention by the animals in the PTZ group [28]. The reference drug sodium valproate reduced the retention transfer latency, increased the recognition index, improved the exploration and free locomotion behavior and ameliorated the spatial memory decline in the animals. Additionally, it mitigated spatial memory decline in the animals, thereby preventing cognitive and memory impairment[86]. This protective effect is attributed to its ability to upregulate GABAergic neurotransmission by counteracting oxidative stress-induced inhibition of glutamate decarboxylase (GAD), ultimately restoring synaptic GABA levels. Since PTZ acts as a reversible antagonist of the GABA-A receptor, the available GABA in the synapse can effectively bind to its receptor, maintaining the glutamate-GABA homeostasis. Such rectifying effects were evident in data from treatment groups as well. Animals receiving cow colostrum exhibited significant reduction in the transfer latency in the retention trial in the elevated plus maze test. The treatment group of animals also showed significantly improved recognition index values and therefore we can conclude that pretreatment with the cow colostrum significantly improved the cognition impairment in the animals. The cow colostrum also reduced anxiety and restored the behavioral normalcy in animals exhibiting their anxiolytic potential. Increased exploration and free movement through central zone in open field test signifies decreased anxiety in the animals [87], [88], [89], [90]. Ameliorated cognitive functions were accompanied with improved memory retention in the treatment group animals. The findings from behavioral and biochemical assessments indicate that cow colostrum exhibits anticonvulsant and antioxidant properties, contributing to the improvement of memory deficits in mice.

Conclusion:

Cow colostrum exerted protective against PTZ induced kindling. The cow colostrum prevented impairment of cognition, memory, and motor coordination in the animals in PTZ induced acute seizure model. Significant neuronal protection was exerted by cow colostrum as it reduced the load of oxidative stress and strengthened antioxidant mechanism in the brain [21], [91], [92] Acute seizure models have limitations such as lack of spontaneous recurrent seizures and of neuronal loss or other neuropathological hallmarks. Therefore, certain parameters such as changes in body weight, the progression of seizures, and the overall effect of cow colostrum in epilepsy require further exploration. Cow colostrum exhibited

therapeutic potential in the PTZ induced acute seizure model which advocates for further studies on identifying its effect in PTZ induced kindling. Future research will explore the effects of prolonged use of cow colostrum on the monoaminergic system and epigenomic mechanisms to uncover the molecular pathways involved in the GABAergic system. Additionally, studies will aim to identify therapeutic targets to better understand how cow colostrum exerts its anticonvulsant properties.

Declaration of competing interest:

The authors have no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments:

The authors would like to thank Amity Institute of Pharmacy (AIP), Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Noida Campus 201313, India for providing facilities for the completion of this research work.

5. Reference:

- [1] K. M. Fiest *et al.*, "Prevalence and incidence of epilepsy," *Neurology*, vol. 88, no. 3, pp. 296–303, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1212/WNL.0000000000003509.
- [2] H. Blumenfeld and J. Taylor, "Why do Seizures Cause Loss of Consciousness?," *The Neuroscientist*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 301–310, Oct. 2003, doi: 10.1177/1073858403255624.
- [3] G. L. Holmes and P.-P. Lenck-Santini, "Role of interictal epileptiform abnormalities in cognitive impairment," *Epilepsy & Behavior*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 504–515, May 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.yebeh.2005.11.014.
- [4] O. Devinsky, "Effects of Seizures on Autonomic and Cardiovascular Function," *Epilepsy Curr*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 43–46, Mar. 2004, doi: 10.1111/j.1535-7597.2004.42001.x.
- [5] O. E. Zubareva *et al.*, "Beneficial Effects of Probiotic Bifidobacterium longum in a Lithium–Pilocarpine Model of Temporal Lobe Epilepsy in Rats," *Int J Mol Sci*, vol. 24, no. 9, p. 8451, May 2023, doi: 10.3390/ijms24098451.
- [6] M. Kandashvili *et al.*, "Myo-Inositol Limits Kainic Acid-Induced Epileptogenesis in Rats," *Int J Mol Sci*, vol. 23, no. 3, p. 1198, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijms23031198.
- [7] A. J. Becker, "Review: Animal models of acquired epilepsy: insights into mechanisms of human epileptogenesis," *Neuropathol Appl Neurobiol*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 112–129, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1111/nan.12451.
- [8] , Adnan Yiiksel, , Müjgan Cengiz, , Mehmet Seven, and , Turgut Ulutin, "Erythrocyte Glutathione, Glutathione Peroxidase, Superoxide Dismutase and Serum Lipid Peroxidation in Epileptic Children With Valproate and Carbamazepine Monotherapy," *J Basic Clin Physiol Pharmacol*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 73–81, Mar. 2000, doi: 10.1515/JBCPP.2000.11.1.73.
- [9] F. Brigo, S. C. Igwe, and A. Del Felice, "Melatonin as add-on treatment for epilepsy," *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, vol. 2016, no. 8, Aug. 2016, doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD006967.pub4.
- [10] B. Halliwell, "The wanderings of a free radical," *Free Radic Biol Med*, vol. 46, no. 5, pp. 531–542, Mar. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2008.11.008.

- [11] R. E. Davis and M. Williams, "Mitochondrial Function and Dysfunction: An Update," *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, vol. 342, no. 3, pp. 598–607, Sep. 2012, doi: 10.1124/jpet.112.192104.
- [12] O. M. E. Abdel-Salam, A. A. Sleem, M. A. E. B. M. Sayed, E. R. Youness, and N. Shaffie, "Capsaicin Exerts Anti-convulsant and Neuroprotective Effects in Pentylenetetrazole-Induced Seizures," *Neurochem Res*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 1045–1061, May 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11064-020-02979-3.
- [13] S. Bhattacharya, "Reactive Oxygen Species and Cellular Defense System," in *Free Radicals in Human Health and Disease*, New Delhi: Springer India, 2015, pp. 17–29. doi: 10.1007/978-81-322-2035-0_2.
- [14] H. Sies, "Oxidative stress: oxidants and antioxidants," *Exp Physiol*, vol. 82, no. 2, pp. 291–295, Mar. 1997, doi: 10.1113/expphysiol.1997.sp004024.
- [15] J. Przybylska, E. Albera, and M. Kankofer, "Antioxidants in Bovine Colostrum," *Reproduction in Domestic Animals*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 402–409, Aug. 2007, doi: 10.1111/j.1439-0531.2006.00799.x.
- [16] M. Ahmadi View *et al.*, "Benefits of bovine colostrum in nutraceutical products," 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://>
- [17] E. Albera and M. Kankofer, "Antioxidants in Colostrum and Milk of Sows and Cows," *Reproduction in Domestic Animals*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 606–611, Aug. 2009, doi: 10.1111/j.1439-0531.2007.01027.x.
- [18] Y. Huang, Z. Wang, Z.-X. Huang, and Z. Liu, "Biomarkers and the outcomes of ischemic stroke," *Front Mol Neurosci*, vol. 16, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.3389/fnmol.2023.1171101.
- [19] D. Lotito *et al.*, "Colostrum Composition, Characteristics and Management for Buffalo Calves: A Review," *Vet Sci*, vol. 10, no. 5, p. 358, May 2023, doi: 10.3390/vetsci10050358.
- [20] S. Mary *et al.*, "ESPÉCIES REATIVAS DE OXIGÊNIO E DE NITROGÊNIO, ANTIOXIDANTES E MARCADORES DE DANO OXIDATIVO EM SANGUE HUMANO: PRINCIPAIS MÉTODOS ANALÍTICOS PARA SUA DETERMINAÇÃO," 2007.
- [21] M. Janusz and A. Zablocka, "Colostrum Proline-Rich Polypeptides – Immunoregulatory Properties and Prospects of Therapeutic Use in Alzheimers Disease," *Curr Alzheimer Res*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 323–333, Jun. 2010, doi: 10.2174/156720510791162377.
- [22] W. Widodo, H. R. P. Kusumaningrum, H. Wihadmadyatami, and A. L. Wicaksana, "Milk Fermented with *Pediococcus acidilactici* Strain BE Improves High Blood Glucose Levels and Pancreatic Beta-Cell Function in Diabetic Rats," *Food Sci Anim Resour*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 170–183, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.5851/kosfa.2022.e69.
- [23] T. C. Ooi, A. Ahmad, N. F. Rajab, and R. Sharif, "The Effects of 12 Weeks Colostrum Milk Supplementation on the Expression Levels of Pro-Inflammatory Mediators and Metabolic Changes among Older Adults: Findings from the Biomarkers and Untargeted Metabolomic Analysis," *Nutrients*, vol. 15, no. 14, p. 3184, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.3390/nu15143184.
- [24] A. Lee, M. C. F. Pontin, E. Kosmerl, R. Jimenez-Flores, D. B. Moretti, and O. Ziouzenkova, "Assessment of adipogenic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties of whole and whey bovine colostrum.," *J Dairy Sci*, vol. 102, no. 10, pp. 8614–8621, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.3168/jds.2019-16509.
- [25] R. F. Squires, E. Saederup, J. N. Crawley, P. Skolnick, and S. M. Paul, "Convulsant potencies of tetrazoles are highly correlated with actions on GABA/benzodiazepine/picrotoxin receptor complexes in brain," *Life Sci*, vol. 35, no. 14, pp. 1439–1444, Oct. 1984, doi: 10.1016/0024-3205(84)90159-0.

- [26] G. M. Everett and R. K. Richards, "Comparative Anticonvulsive Action of 3,5,5-trimethyloxazolidine-2,4-dione (Tridione), Dilantin and Phenobarbital," *Anesthesiology*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 448–448, Jul. 1945, doi: 10.1097/00000542-194507000-00047.
- [27] M. M. Blanco *et al.*, "Assessment of seizure susceptibility in pilocarpine epileptic and nonepileptic Wistar rats and of seizure reinduction with pentylenetetrazole and electroshock models," *Epilepsia*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 824–831, Apr. 2009, doi: 10.1111/j.1528-1167.2008.01797.x.
- [28] P. Mishra, A. K. Mittal, S. K. Rajput, and J. K. Sinha, "Cognition and memory impairment attenuation via reduction of oxidative stress in acute and chronic mice models of epilepsy using antiepileptogenic *Nux vomica*," *J Ethnopharmacol*, vol. 267, p. 113509, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2020.113509.
- [29] A. Tourov, R. Ferri, S. Del Gracco, M. Elia, S. A. Musumeci, and M. C. Stefanini, "Spike morphology in PTZ-induced generalized and cobalt-induced partial experimental epilepsy," *Funct Neurol*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 237–45, 1996.
- [30] M. Mirzababaei *et al.*, "Saccharomyces Boulardii alleviates neuroinflammation and oxidative stress in PTZ-kindled seizure rat model," *Naunyn Schmiedebergs Arch Pharmacol*, Aug. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s00210-024-03361-8.
- [31] V. Mani and S. Rashed Almutairi, "Impact of levetiracetam on cognitive impairment, neuroinflammation, oxidative stress, and neuronal apoptosis caused by lipopolysaccharides in rats," *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, vol. 31, no. 9, p. 101728, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jsps.2023.101728.
- [32] N. Perveen *et al.*, "Perampanel increases seizure threshold in pentylenetetrazole-kindled mice and improves behavioral dysfunctions by modifying mRNA expression levels of BDNF/TrkB and inflammatory markers," *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, vol. 32, no. 1, p. 101930, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jsps.2023.101930.
- [33] A. L. Frantz *et al.*, "Manual acupuncture improves parameters associated with oxidative stress and inflammation in PTZ-induced kindling in mice," *Neurosci Lett*, vol. 661, pp. 33–40, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.neulet.2017.09.044.
- [34] R. J. Claycomb, S. J. Hewett, and J. A. Hewett, "Prophylactic, prandial rofecoxib treatment lacks efficacy against acute PTZ-induced seizure generation and kindling acquisition," *Epilepsia*, p. no-no, Jan. 2011, doi: 10.1111/j.1528-1167.2010.02889.x.
- [35] V. Undale, S. Sangamnerkar, S. Desai, and C. Upasani, "Neuroprotective effect of cow colostrum and tetramethylpyrazine against global cerebral ischemia reperfusion injury," *Int J Nutr Pharmacol Neurol Dis*, vol. 2, no. 2, p. 111, 2012, doi: 10.4103/2231-0738.95947.
- [36] S. Ingale and F. Gandhi, "Effect of aqueous extract of *Moringa oleifera* leaves on pharmacological models of epilepsy and anxiety in mice," *Int J Epilepsy*, vol. 03, no. 01, pp. 012–019, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ijep.2016.02.001.
- [37] M. Mousavi-Hasanzadeh, H. Rezaeian-Varmaziar, O. Shafaat, A. Jand, and M. R. Palizvan, "The effect of co-administration of pentylenetetrazole with pilocarpine: New modified PTZ models of kindling and seizure.," *Pharmacol Biochem Behav*, vol. 182, pp. 7–11, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.pbb.2019.04.010.
- [38] T. Singh, A. Mishra, and R. K. Goel, "PTZ kindling model for epileptogenesis, refractory epilepsy, and associated comorbidities: relevance and reliability," *Metab Brain Dis*, vol. 36, no. 7, pp. 1573–1590, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11011-021-00823-3.
- [39] W. Fischer and H. Kittner, "Influence of ethanol on the pentylenetetrazol-induced kindling in rats," *J Neural Transm*, vol. 105, no. 10–12, pp. 1129–1142, Dec. 1998, doi: 10.1007/s007020050117.

- [40] M. L. Seibenhener and M. C. Wooten, "Use of the Open Field Maze to measure locomotor and anxiety-like behavior in mice.," *J Vis Exp*, no. 96, p. e52434, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.3791/52434.
- [41] V. Carola, F. D'Olimpio, E. Brunamonti, F. Mangia, and P. Renzi, "Evaluation of the elevated plus-maze and open-field tests for the assessment of anxiety-related behaviour in inbred mice," *Behavioural Brain Research*, vol. 134, no. 1–2, pp. 49–57, Aug. 2002, doi: 10.1016/S0166-4328(01)00452-1.
- [42] E. Choleris, "A detailed ethological analysis of the mouse open field test: effects of diazepam, chlordiazepoxide and an extremely low frequency pulsed magnetic field," *Neurosci Biobehav Rev*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 235–260, May 2001, doi: 10.1016/S0149-7634(01)00011-2.
- [43] A. Calvo–Torrent, P. F. Brain, and M. Martinez, "Effect of Predatory Stress on Sucrose Intake and Behavior on the Plus-Maze in Male Mice," *Physiol Behav*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 189–196, Aug. 1999, doi: 10.1016/S0031-9384(99)00051-7.
- [44] P. Hassanzadeh, E. Arbabi, F. Atyabi, and R. Dinarvand, "Ferulic acid exhibits antiepileptogenic effect and prevents oxidative stress and cognitive impairment in the kindling model of epilepsy," *Life Sci*, vol. 179, pp. 9–14, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.lfs.2016.08.011.
- [45] T. M. B. Cavalcante *et al.*, "Ivabradine possesses anticonvulsant and neuroprotective action in mice," *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, vol. 109, pp. 2499–2512, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2018.11.096.
- [46] M. Malaník, M. Čulenová, A. Sychrová, A. Skiba, K. Skalicka-Woźniak, and K. Šmejkal, "Treating Epilepsy with Natural Products: Nonsense or Possibility?," *Pharmaceuticals*, vol. 16, no. 8, p. 1061, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.3390/ph16081061.
- [47] A. Kumar, S. Lalitha, and J. Mishra, "Possible nitric oxide mechanism in the protective effect of hesperidin against pentylenetetrazole (PTZ)-induced kindling and associated cognitive dysfunction in mice.," *Epilepsy Behav*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 103–111, Oct. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.yebeh.2013.06.007.
- [48] H. Ohkawa, N. Ohishi, and K. Yagi, "Assay for lipid peroxides in animal tissues by thiobarbituric acid reaction," *Anal Biochem*, vol. 95, no. 2, pp. 351–358, Jun. 1979, doi: 10.1016/0003-2697(79)90738-3.
- [49] E. S. Bora, R. Karaali, P. Y. Akyol, G. Yurtsever, and O. Erbaş, "The effect of sulfasalazine in pentylenetetrazole-induced seizures in rats," *Brazilian Journal of Medical and Biological Research*, vol. 54, no. 12, 2021, doi: 10.1590/1414-431x2021e11541.
- [50] S. Jayant, B. M. Sharma, R. Bansal, and B. Sharma, "Pharmacological benefits of selective modulation of cannabinoid receptor type 2 (CB2) in experimental Alzheimer's disease," *Pharmacol Biochem Behav*, vol. 140, pp. 39–50, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.pbb.2015.11.006.
- [51] M. Pahuja, J. Mehla, K. H. Reeta, M. Tripathi, and Y. K. Gupta, "Effect of Anacyclus pyrethrum on pentylenetetrazole-induced kindling, spatial memory, oxidative stress and rho-kinase II expression in mice.," *Neurochem Res*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 547–56, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s11064-012-0947-2.
- [52] T. R. Victor, Z. Hage, and S. E. Tsirka, "Prophylactic Administration of Cannabidiol Reduces Microglial Inflammatory Response to Kainate-Induced Seizures and Neurogenesis," *Neuroscience*, vol. 500, pp. 1–11, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2022.06.010.
- [53] S. Tahmasebi, S. Oryan, H. R. Mohajerani, N. Akbari, and M. R. Palizvan, "Probiotics and Nigella sativa extract supplementation improved behavioral and electrophysiological effects of PTZ-induced chemical kindling in rats," *Epilepsy & Behavior*, vol. 104, p. 106897, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.yebeh.2019.106897.

- [54] B. Martinc, I. Grabnar, and T. Vovk, "Antioxidants as a Preventive Treatment for Epileptic Process: A Review of the Current Status," *Curr Neuropharmacol*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 527–550, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.2174/1570159X12666140923205715.
- [55] J. Kaps, V. S. Georgieva, L. Oberholz, A. Kribs, B. Brachvogel, and T. Keller, "Human preterm colostrum stimulates outgrowth in neurogenic tissue," *Pediatr Res*, vol. 94, no. 6, pp. 1906–1910, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1038/s41390-023-02721-z.
- [56] L. Li *et al.*, "Microencapsulation protected *Lactobacillus* viability and its activity in modulating the intestinal microbiota in newly weaned piglets," *J Anim Sci*, vol. 101, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1093/jas/skad193.
- [57] P. Wlaź *et al.*, "Effect of dietary supplementation with *Lactobacillus helveticus* R0052 on seizure thresholds and antiseizure potency of sodium valproate in mice," *Psychopharmacology (Berl)*, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s00213-023-06489-2.
- [58] N. N. Pandey, A. A. Dar, D. B. Mondal, and L. Nagaraja, "Bovine colostrum: A veterinary nutraceutical," 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://www.academicjournals.org/JVMAH>
- [59] S. E. Kim, I. G. Ko, M. S. Shin, C. J. Kim, Y. G. Ko, and H. Cho, "Neuroprotective effects of bovine colostrum on intracerebral hemorrhage-induced apoptotic neuronal cell death in rats.," *Neural Regen Res*, vol. 7, no. 22, pp. 1715–21, Aug. 2012, doi: 10.3969/j.issn.1673-5374.2012.22.006.
- [60] C. Miranda, G. Igrejas, and P. Poeta, "Bovine Colostrum: Human and Animal Health Benefits or Route Transmission of Antibiotic Resistance—One Health Perspective," *Antibiotics*, vol. 12, no. 7, p. 1156, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.3390/antibiotics12071156.
- [61] L.-X. Yang, Y.-Y. Yao, J.-R. Yang, H.-L. Cheng, X.-J. Zhu, and Z.-J. Zhang, "Sphingosine 1-phosphate receptor 1 regulates blood-brain barrier permeability in epileptic mice," *Neural Regen Res*, vol. 0, no. 0, p. 0, 2022, doi: 10.4103/1673-5374.360263.
- [62] T. Shimada and K. Yamagata, "Pentylentetrazole-Induced Kindling Mouse Model," *Journal of Visualized Experiments*, no. 136, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.3791/56573.
- [63] A. I. Qureshi *et al.*, "Extracellular glutamate and other amino acids in experimental intracerebral hemorrhage: an in vivo microdialysis study.," *Crit Care Med*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 1482–9, May 2003, doi: 10.1097/01.CCM.0000063047.63862.99.
- [64] K. R. Lees, "Cerestat and other NMDA antagonists in ischemic stroke," *Neurology*, vol. 49, no. Issue 5, Supplement 4, pp. S66–S69, Nov. 1997, doi: 10.1212/WNL.49.5_Suppl_4.S66.
- [65] Z. Zheng *et al.*, "High-proportion breast milk feeding is associated with a reduction in the incidence of IVH in very preterm infants," *Front Neurol*, vol. 13, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3389/fneur.2022.993985.
- [66] S. S. Vasanthi *et al.*, "Disease-modifying effects of a glial-targeted inducible nitric oxide synthase inhibitor (1400W) in mixed-sex cohorts of a rat soman (GD) model of epilepsy," *J Neuroinflammation*, vol. 20, no. 1, p. 163, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1186/s12974-023-02847-1.
- [67] A. Rajput *et al.*, "Anticonvulsant potential of *Grewia tiliaefolia* in pentylentetrazole induced epilepsy: insights from in vivo and in silico studies," *Metab Brain Dis*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 2355–2367, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11011-023-01252-0.
- [68] K. Okanari *et al.*, "Behavioral and neurotransmitter changes on antiepileptic drugs treatment in the zebrafish pentylentetrazol-induced seizure model," *Behavioural Brain Research*, vol. 464, p. 114920, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.bbr.2024.114920.

- [69] R. Olowe, S. Sandouka, A. Saadi, and T. Shekh-Ahmad, "Approaches for Reactive Oxygen Species and Oxidative Stress Quantification in Epilepsy," *Antioxidants*, vol. 9, no. 10, p. 990, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.3390/antiox9100990.
- [70] C. N. Oliver, P. E. Starke-Reed, E. R. Stadtman, G. J. Liu, J. M. Carney, and R. A. Floyd, "Oxidative damage to brain proteins, loss of glutamine synthetase activity, and production of free radicals during ischemia/reperfusion-induced injury to gerbil brain.," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 87, no. 13, pp. 5144–5147, Jul. 1990, doi: 10.1073/pnas.87.13.5144.
- [71] A. Erdogan, M. A. Erdogan, S. Gurgul, and O. Erbas, "Effects of Diclofenac Sodium on Seizure Activity in Rats with Pentylentetrazole-Induced Convulsions," *Neurochem Res*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 1412–1423, May 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11064-022-03838-z.
- [72] Y. Yang *et al.*, "A Compared Study of Eicosapentaenoic Acid and Docosahexaenoic Acid in Improving Seizure-Induced Cognitive Deficiency in a Pentylentetrazol-Kindling Young Mice Model," *Mar Drugs*, vol. 21, no. 9, p. 464, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.3390/md21090464.
- [73] R. Tambe, P. Jain, S. Patil, P. Ghumatkar, and S. Sathaye, "Antiepileptogenic effects of borneol in pentylentetrazole-induced kindling in mice," *Naunyn Schmiedebergs Arch Pharmacol*, vol. 389, no. 5, pp. 467–475, May 2016, doi: 10.1007/s00210-016-1220-z.
- [74] N. Soni, P. Koushal, B. V. K. Reddy, R. Deshmukh, and P. Kumar, "Effect of GLT-1 modulator and P2X7 antagonists alone and in combination in the kindling model of epilepsy in rats," *Epilepsy & Behavior*, vol. 48, pp. 4–14, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.yebeh.2015.04.056.
- [75] M. Pahuja, J. Mehla, K. H. Reeta, M. Tripathi, and Y. K. Gupta, "Effect of Anacyclus pyrethrum on Pentylentetrazole-Induced Kindling, Spatial Memory, Oxidative Stress and Rho-Kinase II Expression in Mice," *Neurochem Res*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 547–556, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s11064-012-0947-2.
- [76] L. Kandratavicius *et al.*, "Animal models of epilepsy: use and limitations," *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat*, p. 1693, Sep. 2014, doi: 10.2147/NDT.S50371.
- [77] R. Dringen, J. M. Gutterer, and J. Hirrlinger, "Glutathione metabolism in brain," *Eur J Biochem*, vol. 267, no. 16, pp. 4912–4916, Aug. 2000, doi: 10.1046/j.1432-1327.2000.01597.x.
- [78] G. S. Taiwe, T. B. Tchoya, J. R. Menanga, B. Dabole, and M. De Waard, "Anticonvulsant activity of an active fraction extracted from *Crinum jagus* L. (Amaryllidaceae), and its possible effects on fully kindled seizures, depression-like behaviour and oxidative stress in experimental rodent models," *J Ethnopharmacol*, vol. 194, pp. 421–433, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2016.10.023.
- [79] F. Yakmaz, A. S. Bozkurt, and Ş. Görücü Yilmaz, "PTZ-kindled rat model; evaluation of seizure, hippocampal EGR-1, and Rev-erb α gene regulation, behavioral analysis, and antioxidant capacity of Gum Arabic," *Mol Biol Rep*, vol. 51, no. 1, p. 279, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s11033-024-09210-4.
- [80] R. Joshi, K. H. Reeta, S. K. Sharma, M. Tripathi, and Y. K. Gupta, "Panchagavya Ghrita, an Ayurvedic formulation attenuates seizures, cognitive impairment and oxidative stress in pentylentetrazole induced seizures in rats.," *Indian J Exp Biol*, vol. 53, no. 7, pp. 446–51, Jul. 2015.
- [81] M. Pahuja, J. Mehla, and Y. Kumar Gupta, "Anticonvulsant and antioxidative activity of hydroalcoholic extract of tuber of *Orchis mascula* in pentylentetrazole and maximal electroshock induced seizures in rats," *J Ethnopharmacol*, vol. 142, no. 1, pp. 23–27, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2012.04.006.

- [82] A. G. de Souza *et al.*, "Prevention of pentylentetrazole-induced kindling and behavioral comorbidities in mice by levetiracetam combined with the GLP-1 agonist liraglutide: Involvement of brain antioxidant and BDNF upregulating properties," *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, vol. 109, pp. 429–439, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2018.10.066.
- [83] T. Hayase, "Working memory- and anxiety-related behavioral effects of repeated nicotine as a stressor: the role of cannabinoid receptors," *BMC Neurosci*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 20, Dec. 2013, doi: 10.1186/1471-2202-14-20.
- [84] G. Biala and M. Kruk, "Cannabinoid receptor ligands suppress memory-related effects of nicotine in the elevated plus maze test in mice," *Behavioural Brain Research*, vol. 192, no. 2, pp. 198–202, Oct. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.bbr.2008.04.004.
- [85] A. G. de Souza *et al.*, "Prevention of pentylentetrazole-induced kindling and behavioral comorbidities in mice by levetiracetam combined with the GLP-1 agonist liraglutide: Involvement of brain antioxidant and BDNF upregulating properties," *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, vol. 109, pp. 429–439, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2018.10.066.
- [86] X. Li *et al.*, "Cannabidiol attenuates seizure susceptibility and behavioural deficits in adult CDKL5^{R59X} knock-in mice," *European Journal of Neuroscience*, vol. 59, no. 12, pp. 3337–3352, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.1111/ejn.16350.
- [87] A. L. Greggor, A. Thornton, and N. S. Clayton, "Neophobia is not only avoidance: improving neophobia tests by combining cognition and ecology," *Curr Opin Behav Sci*, vol. 6, pp. 82–89, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.cobeha.2015.10.007.
- [88] G. R. Brown and C. Nemes, "The exploratory behaviour of rats in the hole-board apparatus: Is head-dipping a valid measure of neophilia?," *Behavioural Processes*, vol. 78, no. 3, pp. 442–448, Jul. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.beproc.2008.02.019.
- [89] B. L. Aguilar, L. Malkova, P. N'Gouemo, and P. A. Forcelli, "Genetically Epilepsy-Prone Rats Display Anxiety-Like Behaviors and Neuropsychiatric Comorbidities of Epilepsy," *Front Neurol*, vol. 9, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.3389/fneur.2018.00476.
- [90] K.-R. Shieh and S.-C. Yang, "Exploratory and agile behaviors with central dopaminergic activities in open field tests in Formosan wood mice (*Apodemus semotus*)," *Journal of Experimental Biology*, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1242/jeb.199356.
- [91] M. G. Stewart, "Colostrinin: a naturally occurring compound derived from mammalian colostrum with efficacy in treatment of neurodegenerative diseases, including Alzheimer's," *Expert Opin Pharmacother*, vol. 9, no. 14, pp. 2553–9, Oct. 2008, doi: 10.1517/14656566.9.14.2553.
- [92] H. S. Choi *et al.*, "Neuroprotective effects of consuming bovine colostrum after focal brain ischemia/reperfusion injury in rat model," *Nutr Res Pract*, vol. 4, no. 3, p. 196, 2010, doi: 10.4162/nrp.2010.4.3.196.